

115966 – PREFER

**Patient Preferences in Benefit-Risk Assessments during the Drug Life
Cycle**

The PREFER Deliverables

Lead contributor	The PREFER consortium
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Document History

Version	Date	Description
V1.0	8 December 2021	First version
V2.0	3 February 2022	Updated list

Introduction

Patients' preferences are a growing topic of interest, and stakeholders (e.g. regulators, payers, industry, and patient organizations) have called for greater involvement of patients. The objective of PREFER is to guide industry, regulatory authorities and HTA bodies and reimbursement agencies on how patient preferences can be assessed and used to inform medical product decision making by developing expert and evidence-based recommendations.

In below list the main deliverables of PREFER are listed together with a link to the material.

Title	Link
Desires, expectations, concerns and requirements of stakeholders about methodologies for patient-preference elicitation and their use in making well-informed decisions regarding medicinal products	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5499904
Processes, conditions and contextual factors that influence the utility and role of patient preference studies	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5727430
Identification of assessment criteria used at decision points throughout the medical product lifecycle	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5750113
Report on methods for measuring patient benefit-risk preferences in medical treatment	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5727440
Identification of educational and psychological feature methods	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5750154
Characterising and appraising the methods	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5763873
Identification of candidate methodologies and criteria to assess empirical case and simulation studies	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5763889
Determine research questions and assessment criteria for the preference studies used in the empirical case studies	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5763902
Translate the preliminary research questions identified in WP2 to concrete study designs	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5865307
Historical Case Studies (D3.3)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6389861
PREFER recommendations (D4.3)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6470922
Operational Guidance (D4.4)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6400552
Summary report on training materials (D4.5)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6397608
Sustainability Plan (D1.7)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6599962
Data Management Plan (D1.9)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6599930

Case studies

Title	Link
D 3.5 Report of case study RA (preventive treatment)	Link to IAHPR's study registry HPSTR: https://hpstr.org/record/190184/001/040/entry <i>Link to study protocol:</i> http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2020-045851

	<p><i>Link to plain language summary:</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5744859</p> <p><i>Link to study report:</i> <i>Will be accessible on zenodo after publication of the study</i></p>
D 3.6 Report of case study NMD	<p><i>Link to IAHPR's study registry HPSTR:</i> https://hpstr.org/record/190182/001/025/entry</p> <p><i>Link to study protocol:</i> https://doi.org/10.12688/wellcomeopenres.16116.1</p> <p><i>Link to plain language summary:</i></p> <p><i>Link to study report:</i> <i>Will be accessible on zenodo after publication of the study</i></p>
D 3.7 Report of case study lung cancer	<p><i>Link to IAHPR's study registry HPSTR:</i> https://hpstr.org/record/190183/001/029/entry</p> <p><i>Link to study protocol:</i> https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2021.689114</p> <p><i>Link to plain language summary:</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6260511</p> <p><i>Link to study report:</i> <i>Will be accessible on zenodo after publication of the study</i></p>
D 3.8 Report on additional case studies	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5865369</p>
Case study on Rheumatoid arthritis: Treatment options	See 3.8 above
Case study on Diabetes	See 3.8 above
Case study on Multiple Myeloma	See 3.8 above
Case study on Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD)	See 3.8 above
Case study on Chronic pain	See 3.8 above
Case study on Myocardial infarction	See 3.8 above
Case study on PAVING: Gene therapy in haemophilia	See 3.8 above
D 3.9 Report assessing the outcomes of the case studies versus criteria from WP 2	<i>Will be accessible on zenodo after publication</i>
D 3.10 Report assessing the extent to which results of case studies can be translated to other disease areas	<i>Will be accessible on zenodo after publication</i>